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**Why does Al-Jazeera Carry Reports of Terrorist
Organizations?
And does it therefore Support Terrorism?**

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Abstract

This research aims to identify and discuss the reasons of why the Qatari based channel Al-Jazeera opens its air to terrorist organizations, particularly Al-Qaida and its leader Osama ben Ladin, and transmits their messages. To do so, based on critical media/ cultural study approach, which allows the researcher to narrate and analyze the data in a comprehensive way, this research has been contextualized by providing a literature about the nature of relationship between media and terrorism.

The data of this research about Al-Jazeera, terrorism and Al-Qaida are collected basically from books, academic journals and conference proceedings. However, the findings of this research are the conclusion extracted as result of the discussed materials.

1. Introduction

Dealing with terrorism and media would actually be a huge subject, but this brief discussion aims to shed light on a case study related to this field of academia. This study focuses on a contemporary issue in the field of media and terrorism. It aims to understand how and why a famous media outlet transmits or carries terrorists' messages; "*Why does Al-Jazeera carry reports of terrorist organizations? And does it therefore support terrorism?*".

This research is divided into an Introduction and two major sections. The Introduction postulates the research questions, aims, objectives and methodology. The First Section is concerned in tracing the historical debate about media and terrorism to contextualize the research and provide background information. However, the Second Section answers the research's questions, through engaging with the opposing arguments about Al-Jazeera's controversial reporting of terrorists' messages.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Many studies have focused on Al-Jazeera as a salient media phenomenon in the Middle East which airs controversial materials, including Al-Qaida videotapes (e.g. El Nawawy & Iskandar, 2002). However, these researches did not focus on the nature of relation between this media outlet and the notorious organization Al-Qaida. To bridge the gap in the current literature, this research investigates the reasons of why Al-Jazeera reports terrorists' messages. It hinges on an idea that there is an intersection of interests between Al-Jazeera and Al-Qaida.

1.2 Research Aims

This major aim of this research is to find out the reasons which lead Al-Jazeera to transmit the terrorists' messages, particularly Al-Qaida in the Middle East. However, there are two sub-aims:

- To find out why does Al-Qaida choose Al-Jazeera to transmit its messages
- To find out Al-Jazeera mechanism in airing Al-Qaida videotapes

1.3 Research Questions

To achieve the aim of this research, the major question and its related sub-question, as shown in the title, are:

The main question is: Why does Al-Jazeera carry reports of terrorist organizations?

The related sub-question is: And does it therefore support terrorism?

1.4 Research Objectives

To answer the research's questions, the following objectives are used:

- Undertaken a literature review the relation between media and terrorism
- Undertaken a literature review about the history of Al-Jazeera
- Undertaken a literature review about Al-Qaida media strategy
- Collecting and analyzing the archival data about Al-Jazeera airing of Osama ben Ladin's videotapes

1.5 Significance and Contribution to Knowledge

This research is significant, because it sheds light on a contemporary issue in media and terrorism whereas many researchers have not dealt with adequately. In this context, this short thesis contributes to the existed researches in this field by showing how the

intersection of interests occurs between a famous media outlet and a notorious terrorist organization in the era of war on terror.

However, there are limitations in this research. Due to the fact that number of words is limited, this research may not cover all aspects of the investigated issue. Furthermore, the collected materials are in English and there are no Arabic materials approached by the researcher.

1.6 Research Method and Theoretical Framework

This research situates in the field of qualitative research, because quantitative researches consider measurements techniques to show frequencies or compare between variables (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005). However, this research merges between historical outlook and analytical perspective, the methodology is crucial to argue critically, instead of dealing descriptively. As result of the critical paradigmatic stance which considers different factors that shape the reality and emphasizes on the researcher's voice (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005), this research fits in qualitative research field.

In his argument to develop the approach critical media/ cultural studies, Kellner (2009) points out that "the media industries are a powerful institution in contemporary societies and it is essential to comprehend how they work in order to understand, act in, and transform the environment in which we live our lives" (p. 5).

Considering Al-Jazeera, which transmits terrorists' messages, and Al-Qaida media strategy, the approach critical media/ cultural studies serves this research to discuss and understand the media policy of the Qatari based channel and outline if there are mutual interests with Al-Qaida and consequently what is the nature of these interests.

In media studies, there are several theories each has its ideological background or related to the developments in communication technologies (Bennett, 1982; Holmes, 2005). This research considers the social responsibility theory as a theoretical framework, because the focus is on Al-Jazeera. On contrary, agenda-setting theory may be appropriate if the focus

of the study is on a terrorist media outlet.

Social responsibility theory has been developed in the democratic countries and its main assumption is the audience “has the right to know” (Kirsten, 2007, p. 461). However, this right to inform is not extreme, because the responsibility has limitations. Kirsten (2007), who discussed media and terrorism in the light of many theories, including social responsibility theory, argues that, “The media have a responsibility towards the population in terms of being informative, but also in maintaining their own credibility” (p. 465).

This theory considers a framework in this research. In this vein, this research to be contextualised discusses media responsibility in reporting terrorism.

2. Media and Terrorism... The Bilateral Relation

This section provides background of media and terrorism to contextualize this research. It discusses three issues: terrorism as a form of communication, media and terrorism before and after 9/11, and media responsibility in reporting terrorism. However, it is crucial in the beginning to provide a definition of terrorism.

2.1 Definition of Terrorism

Terrorism has a global impact, however, there is no international consensus on its definition. But, this research adopts a definition of terrorism to provide a foundation of the debates and arguments. In this regard, this research adopts the following definition of terrorism: “The use of violence to target non-combatants (‘innocents’ in the *jus in bello* sense) for political purposes” (Frey & Wellman, 2003, p. 263).

This definition will serve the ultimate aim of the thesis, because it could be applied to any organization, state and person, who are using deliberately violence against innocents, whatever their intention or their goal. Thus, this definition of terrorism can be applied on organizations such as Al-Qaida and its members.

2.2 Terrorism as a Form of Communication

Terrorism has become a global phenomenon in recent years whereas some researchers find it a form of violent and bloody communication. Schmid and de Graaf argue that “terrorism can best be understood as a violent communication strategy. There is a sender, the terrorist, a message generator, the victim, and a receiver, the enemy and/or the public. The nature of the terrorist act, its atrocity, its location and the identity of its victim serve as a generator for the power of the message” (cited in Schlesinger et al., p. 156).

In this context, the relationship between terrorism and the media postulated a new term “media-oriented terrorism” to point out that terrorists intend from their acts to entice media

and public attention (Martin, 2010).

In this vein, Suter (2008) agrees with Martin that the best vehicle for publicising terrorism is the media. Based on Martin and Suter's arguments, it could be observed that terrorism may suffer without media. As noted previously, terrorism in itself is a form of communication, but it needs the media to achieve its goal.

Regarding the nature of media outlets, which transmit terrorism, the television is considered historically one of the most important mediums to report bloody events.

Schlesinger et al. (1983) argue that television news is probably the main source of footage of terrorism for audience, because television is widely seen by the public and it may have an impact on the public. Similarly, Lewis (2005) asserts that, "Television remains the most widespread and significant medium in the global communication of terror and political violence" (p. 7)

Due to its audio-visual characteristic, Schlesinger et al. (1983) find out that television has attracted and reinforced all the arguments that grew up around these older media. They argue that "television as a privileged place in the debate on 'terrorism' has been further secured by the rise of counter-insurgency theories which see the state fighting a continuing battle for hearts and minds, in which television as the dominant mass medium, plays a strategic role" (ibid, 143).

Likewise, terrorists and terrorist organizations have known early the importance of television and consider it their favorable medium to promulgate their messages and broadcast their activities (Chaliand, 1987; Martin, 2010).

Notably, there is a difference between television and print media in reporting terrorism. However, television focuses on the event itself rather than the context and circumstances (Dobkin, 1992). This argument has been built on the fact that, "Television news coverage lends immediacy and adds a dimension of drama not captured in print media. Reports of terrorism presented on television constitute high drama due to the compelling nature of

coverage, the centrality of personalities, the intense emotional and symbolic content, and the priestly role adopted by news personalities” (Dobkin, 1992, p. 4).

The dramatized coverage of terrorism sometimes becomes unusual, because it exaggerates the event. This is the main problem when television screens terrorists’ acts or interviews. Nacos (1994) agrees with the arguments that emphasize on the importance of television in its coverage, however, she points out that, “It has been charged time and again that television coverage of terrorism is excessive and that the media blows the importance of these events out of proportion” (p. 56).

On contrary, print media in some cases and for certain reasons could be more reliable sources of information about terrorists’ acts than television. In her study of the Italian press, especially in the first days of Aldo Moro’s kidnapping and assassination in 1978 by the Red Brigades, Wagner-Pacifici (1986) concludes that the printed media played a pivotal role in the coverage more than media of the airwaves and “perhaps this indicates something about the need of interpreters to slowly work with and work over the texts of a social drama, something the speed and ephemerality of the airwave media do not allow. In fact, the number of television viewers actually declined during the Moro affair” (p. 18).

On the other hand, terrorists are tending to exploit the media to transmit their messages. This notion has been observed and discussed by many researchers, as well as politicians and terrorists themselves who agree that the media is crucial.

To give notice to their actions, terrorists find out that media a useful tool to transmit their political messages. This issue has been observed by the politician William Whitelaw, the former Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, who points out that, “The principal object of the terrorists’ acts of violence is to draw attention to themselves and gain notoriety... They bomb and murder their way into the headlines” (cited in Schlesinger et al., 1983, p. 12).

In this regard, some academics agree that terrorists consider their actions as a device to

maximize publicity and entice public attentions; because the media outlets will cover their violence (Frey & Wellman 2003; Schaffert 1992).

In this vein, Qureshi (2009) argues that, “The new media has provided a perfect vehicle for terrorists to transmit their message and now the terrorists have learnt to manipulate the media as well” (p. 225). He (ibid) points out that, “The aim of terrorists in carrying out their heinous attack is to get attention, thereby get recognition and aspire to achieve legitimacy for their actions. The media provides the platform to achieve three objectives” (p. 227).

As many terrorists and terrorist organizations try to hear their voices and transmit their messages for the public, they have established directly and indirectly relationships with some reporters (Martin, 2010). In this regard, there are many examples of the relationships between journalists and terrorists. An example is the attendance of Al-Jazeera Syrian journalist, Ahmad Zeidan – who produced the documentary ‘Ben Ladin Unmasked’ - the wedding feast of ben Ladin’s son (Tatham 2006). Another example is the case of Tayseer Alluni, Al-Jazeera’s former reporter in Afghanistan, who was sentenced to seven years’ jail in 2005, because the court found out he was collaborated with Al-Qaida (Lia, 2008).

From a terrorist’s point of view, Hans Joachim Klein, the former member of the German left-wing militant group, who participated in the attack against the Headquarter of The Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in the Austrian Capital Vienna in 1975, confided to Der Spiegel: “We... asked ourselves... what would be an action that no one can disregard, that everyone must talk about in the media and report on. We found it: a bomb. Even though the bomb did not explode, this story went halfway around the world” (cited in Weimann & Winn, 1994, p. 118).

In their dealings with media outlets, some researchers argue that terrorists try to succeed in sending their messages. If successful, terrorists can transmit their messages and images to million houses throughout the world, and thus they may succeed in enticing some

audiences to their side if they embedded their messages with sentimental content (Martin, 2010).

Thus, the publicity is in the hand of the media outlets which have the control on what to transmit to the public (Nacos, 1994). In this vein, Paul Wilkinson argues that, “The free media in an open society are particularly vulnerable to exploitation and manipulation by ruthless terrorist organizations... The media are almost bound to respond to terrorist propaganda of the deed because it is dramatic bad news” (cited in Venkatraman, 2004, pp. 106-108).

However, the lacked notion in the argument is how terrorists exploit the media. Based on the literature, it seems obviously that media outlets cover terrorists’ acts because they are bad news. However, this research will discuss how free media should report terrorism at the end of this section.

2.3 Media and Terrorism after 9/11

The attacks against the United States on September 11, 2001 were a historical event in the world of terrorism and counterterrorism. People in the United States and throughout the world watched on television, on that day, the dramatic fall of the twin towers of the World Trade Centre in New York.

To deal with this phenomenon of media and terrorism on the post 9/11 era, it is important to shed light on media and terrorism before 9/11, where this relationship had been discussed by many academics.

Goodin (2006) argues that, “‘Terrorism’ is one subject that is particularly prone to being over reported in the media. This had been true well before 11 September 2001” (pp. 134-135).

Due to its importance in the last century, terrorists were aware about the importance of media alongside with their actions. Rosie (1986) observes that, “From the mid-1960s it became possible for a terrorist group to hijack an aircraft (or ship) anywhere in the world

and have news of the event flashed round the globe within hours” (p. 24).

But there were few terrorist events viewed globally by millions of people, despite of the limitation of communication technologies in that era. Nacos (2002) points out to two major terrorist events viewed by millions,

“After President John F. Kennedy was assassinated in 1963, most Americans and many people abroad eventually saw the fatal shots and the ensuing events on television. But beyond the United States and Western countries, far fewer people abroad owned television sets at the time. When the Palestinian ‘Black September’ group attacked and killed members of the Israeli team during the 1972 Olympic games in Munich, (using their surviving victims as human shields during their ill-fated escape), an estimated eight hundred million people around the globe watched the unfolding tragedy” (p. 37).

In the last event, Dobkin (1992) states that, “ABC News provided the first live, international coverage of a terrorist act during broadcast of the 1972 Munich Olympic Games” (p. 5). This may indicate that the ‘Black September’ group benefited from the global athletic event and thus its attack gained a wide media coverage.

One of the arguments, which emerged after the mid of 1970s, is that covering terrorism by media has a contagion effect, because it serves in spreading terrorism whereas some terrorists consider the actions of other terrorists a model can be followed, such hijacking of aircrafts (Dobkin, 1992; Kirsten, 2007).

In 1981, there was a turning point in the United States when President Reagan provided in his inaugural address the starting point for examining the emergence of the terrorist threat (Dobkin, 1992). In this regard, the global status quo of terrorism in 1980s led to an academic explanation on television about this phenomenon. As Dobkin (1992) observes

that, “With the growing fear of terrorism in the 1980s has come an abundance of institutional research and a proliferation of experts who offer simple explanations of television’s contribution to the problem of terrorism” (p. 2).

This means that the phenomenon of terrorism requires explanations from academics and experts on the media, and not only the coverage. However, Goodin (2006) denies any relation between the increase of terrorism due to media reporting of terrorist acts. “A 1987 study of coverage of international terrorist incidents by television news, for example, found that there was no systematic relation between the frequency of news reports and the frequency of actual terrorist incidents, worldwide” (Goodin, 2006, p. 135).

The problem is not with Goodin’s argument, which is based on an empirical study in 1987; however, the problem is in the responsibility of the media on how it should report terrorism. This issue will be discussed in the coming section.

On the other hand, the media after 9/11 has become more aware of the phenomenon of terrorism, because the attacks on the United States were televised. Goodin (2006) finds out that, “With September 11, of course, US television coverage of terrorism soared. The number of news stories about terrorism on the three major networks [in the United States] jumped from around 178 in the 12 months prior to September 11 to 1345 stories in the twelve months afterwards” (p. 135).

This massive coverage has been noticed by academics dealing with media and terrorism. One of the observations is the change of the discourse within the media when it deals with terrorism, after the United States’ launch of the ‘global war on terror.’

Qureshi (2009) argues that, “We must accept that the 9/11 attack brought about a significant change in the global view on terrorism. The entire media even the global broadcasters like CNN are committed to the ‘US Patriotic Act’” (p. 224).

It could be observed from Goodin and Qureshi’s arguments that the September attacks were a turning point in reporting of terrorism, where the then American administration

played a major role in using the media to change the global view on terrorism.

In this regard, Brinson and Stohl (2009) observe that, “As we have seen in the context of the Bush administration in the aftermath of September 11 the government frame may also serve to constitute the very definition of the problem as the media overwhelmingly adopted the language of the ‘global war on terror’ when reporting terrorism” (p. 230).

These arguments are applicable on the case of reporting terrorism in the United States, but it would be difficult to observe any existence of a global consensus on terrorism, and it is hard to find a global language on how media should report terrorism. The next subsection deals with media responsibility in reporting terrorism.

2.4 Media Responsibility in Reporting Terrorism

The debate about media responsibility in reporting terrorism among academics and politicians goes back to the end of 1970s, especially in the United States and the United Kingdom.

In this vein, Rosie (1986) refers to the debates in the early 1980s between governments and media, especially in the United States and the United Kingdom,

“Increasingly Western governments (and in particular those of Britain and the USA) are arguing that terrorism cannot be defeated until the Western media stop playing into the hands of terrorists by providing saturation coverage of every major incident. The media (and particularly the American media) respond by saying that what is happening must be reported, and the phenomenon with which they are confronted. These arguments were vigorously aired during and after the hijacking of a TWA jet to Beirut in June 1985 when the American TV crews were given access to the hostages, and relayed day-by-day, often live coverage of the events home to the United States. In Britain, the BBC fell foul of the British government in 1985 for planning to broadcast television interviews with two Ulster extremists, one of

whom had been a leading light in the provisional IRA [Irish Republican Army]” (p. 25).

For some politicians and academics, the media represents an important platform for terrorists, arguing that the media should deprive terrorists of transmitting their messages. Thus, the former British Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher concluded when the Irish Republican Army violence was reaching a peak that, “Publicity is the oxygen of terrorism” (cited in Qureshi, 2009, p. 237).

Nacos (2002) agrees with Thatcher’s comment and asserts that the, “Former British Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher had it right when she proclaimed the publicity is the oxygen of terrorism. If anything has changed in the last ten or fifteen years, it is the increased availability of the sort of oxygen Mrs. Thatcher warned of and upon which mass-mediated terrorism thrives” (p. 27).

Goodin (2006) comments on Thatcher’s phrase, pointing out it was “employed by British home secretary, Douglas Hurd, in 1988 when invoking his powers under the Broadcasting Act to outlaw the radio or television broadcasting of speeches by representatives or supporters of various named organizations involved in The Troubles...” (p. 131).

In this regard, Goodin (2006) warns media outlets from transmitting terrorists’ reports, because they may intend to gain legitimacy or to fear the public.

These arguments are no longer applicable, because politicians, academics and researchers should seek other ways to counter terrorists’ propaganda, especially with the progress of new communication technologies. Some governments have tried to control terrorists’ messages. But this does not stop the fear of people and inhibits finding a useful way for the media to deal with terrorists’ messages.

In their studying UK and US newspapers’ coverage of the London attacks on 7 July 2005 and the transatlantic terror plot on 8 October 2006, Brinson and Stohl (2009) conclude that, “The media coverage in these particular situations, seem to ‘err’ on the side of the

government, by creating frames in the news supportive of the government position, as opposed to providing the terrorist with the ‘oxygen’ they seek to have their message prevail” (p. 243). Thus, “When President Bush said to the country that Americans are vulnerable to weapons of mass destruction in the hands of terrorists, for example, the media headlined those comments and effectively magnified the public’s fears” (Moeller, 2008, p. 7). Hence, the role of politicians and media are crucial to increase or decrease fears.

One of the important issues is the negative influence of terrorists’ messages on public opinion. Norris argues that “one sided messages of terrorism will influence public opinion, how people evaluate terrorism and its actors, and perceptions of future risk and threats” (cited in Brinson and Stohl, 2009, pp. 229-230). Similarly, Qureshi (2009) agrees with Norris’ argument pointing out to the damaging effect of media outlets on the audience when they transmit terrorists’ messages as facts.

From governmental perspective, the public media can adopt the policy of the state in reporting terrorism. This has been verified clearly by the previous arguments. However, there is still the issue of the private media, which is often accused of spreading fear when reporting terrorism and relaying terrorist messages. Notably, reporting terrorism in Western democracies is one of the important issues, because the media in these countries is liberal in general and terrorists may benefit from the freedom of press (Weimann & Winn, 1994).

Officials and academics observe the danger of reporting terrorism and thus they ask media to put editorial criteria. Clarke (2003) argues that,

“Terrorists need the media to spread the fear that the terrorist wishes to create. But at the same time terrorists generally stand for intolerance and do not support openness. Terrorists fear new ideas; new religions and they see the modern world as a threat, not an opportunity. It is the role of the media

to create a more open world. The terrorist who manipulates the media in the short run will come to be fearful of the media as they seek to better inform the public about the narrowness of terrorist ambition” (p. 66).

However, there is always an intersection point between media and terrorism. This point is related to the need of media, especially the private media, to report terrorism and the need of terrorists for the media. This relationship is described as “a symbiotic relationship” (Ghetti, 2008, p. 489).

When the media reports terrorist acts, it serves the aim of terrorists and encourages other terrorist groups to engage in more terrorism. Ghetti (2008) argues that terrorists are inspired by the actions of other terrorists, and thus there is a possibility the inspired terrorists may increase their attacks which is reinforced by publicity provided by media.

In addition, terrorists may send hidden codes in their messages. Martin (2010) warns media in its reporting terrorism, arguing “It is conceivable that interviews with terrorists, media scooping, and other reporting practices may send messages to terrorists, encourage supporters, cause victims to react, engage the target in a global forum, elicit sympathy and convince political and journalistic analysts to affix favourable labels to the group or movement” (p. 395).

However, Nacos (1994) has an opposite argument, pointing out that the public does not accept the argument that terrorist violence would not occur if media organizations simply stopped reporting terrorism.

Nacos’s argument is true on the one hand that the media cannot stop terrorist acts. On the other hand, this argument ignores the influence that the media has when reporting terrorist acts. Ghetti and Martin’s arguments are crucial in verifying the potential role of the media in supporting terrorism. They warn of the media’s negative influence when reporting terrorist acts.

In his discussing the American media coverage of terrorism, Jenkins (2003) argues that,

“When we read or watch media coverage of terrorism, we have to understand the limits of what media knows, what they can say, and how completely even the most critical journalists depend on the good will of federal law enforcement and intelligence agencies. Yet the news media are not the only way that people form their images of terrorism” (p. 138).

Seemingly, the lack of a world consensus on the definition of terrorism prevents the existence of a useful criterion on how media should report terrorism. The debate on this issue goes back to the 1980s. Schlesinger et al. (1983), who focused on discussing the televising of the Irish Republican Army actions and messages in the United Kingdom, agree with the argument that since terrorism is outside the consensus, broadcasters do not feel obliged to treat it in a balanced or impartial manner.

The same authors, who discussed the power of media during conflicts, requested from media to ensure its diversity principle and availability to everyone.

Based on this argument, media should report terrorism. However, reporting terrorism in the post-9/11 era may threaten media credibility. Otherwise, the media may be accused of irresponsibility even if there is no global consensus on the definition of terrorism (Venkatraman, 2004).

Thus, the major problem is not in the definition, but in the media policy. In this regard, Venkatraman (2004) argues that social responsibility is the solution to save media and the public from the influence of terrorists. Similarly, Suter (2008) argues that, “The media must be responsible in how they report terrorist attacks. Otherwise, they may find they are part of the problem, rather than the solution” (pp. 277-278).

It has been made clear from these arguments that media outlets should be aware when they report terrorism. They should be responsible for delivering news professionally, not the terrorists’ messages.

A resolution on terrorism and the media adopted by the participants in the Conference on

Terrorism and Media held in Manila on 1 and 2 May 2002 agrees with the right of media to report on terrorism, but in a responsible way:

“The media have both a right and a duty to report fully on terrorism in the interest of the public’s right to know and to promote open, informed debate about terrorism; All parties to conflicts should respect the right of journalists to investigate and report freely on conflict and to have maximum access to conflict areas.

The threat of terrorism should not be used as an excuse to impose restrictions on the right to freedom of expression and of the media, or on freedom of information, and specifically on the following rights: to editorial independence; to protect confidential sources of information; to access information held by public bodies; to freedom of movement; and to privacy of communications.

Media outlets, journalists and publishers and broadcasters associations, academic institutions and other civil society organisations should take measures to enhance the capacity of the media to report professionally on terrorism and to promote tolerance, including through training and providing opportunities for discussion of ethical issues relating to reporting on terrorism” (Boafo & Coudray, 2003, p. 127).

Adopting a definition of terrorism is crucial for media outlets to know the limits when they report terrorist acts. But this does not mean, because of the absence of a definition, that any media outlet is free from responsibility in reporting terrorism, because it may unwittingly support terrorism.

In summary, it is the responsibility of the media to report terrorism in a professional and ethical way. However, the absence of an international measurement will result in every media outlet adopting its own explanation of responsibility when it reports terrorism. This

can be clearly observed in the case of Al-Jazeera, which conveys terrorist messages, and the next section will deal with this case. Thus, the solution can be emerged from the media outlet itself by setting a policy and defining clearly its understanding of terrorism.

3. Al-Jazeera Case in Reporting Terrorism

Unlike the previous section which contextualized the research, this section deals with the heart of the research, explaining why Al-Jazeera reports terrorists' messages, Al-Qaida's media strategy and concluding whether Al-Jazeera is supporting terrorism or not.

3.1 Al-Jazeera's Emergence in the World of 'War on Terror'

One of the controversial channels in the world is Al-Jazeera, particularly after its airing videotapes Al-Qaida leader Osama ben Ladin since 1999 (Azran, 2007).

Al-Jazeera, which is an Arabic news channel, born in 1996, when the Emir of Qatar, Hamad ben Khalifa, recruited staff members of the short-lived BBC Arabic Television and invested US \$140 million to start his channel (Seib, 2008). It is estimated that approximately 70% of Arabs are watching Al-Jazeera (Rinnawi, 2006).

This channel has an impact on the Arab world. As Rushing (2007) argues this channel changed Arabs perception about the news likewise Henry Ford changed the way Americans thought about choosing the vehicle to travel.

However, the debates about this channel started after its airing of an exclusive interview with the head of Al-Qaida, Osama ben Ladin on the 10th of June 1999 after his organization bombed the American embassies in the African cities Kenya and Tanzania (El-Nawawy & Iskander, 2002).

The fame of Al-Jazeera in the international scene has soared since the September attacks in 2001. One of the main reasons for Al-Jazeera's fame is its exclusive access to Al-Qaida messages and its terrorist leaders. Remarkably, this channel was praised, particularly from Americans, for its freedom of press standards before it started airing terrorists' videotapes (Miles, 2005).

Al-Jazeera reported Osama ben Ladin and Al-Qaida's messages many times after the September attacks. On October 5, 2001, Al-Jazeera aired footage of Al-Qaida's leader ben Ladin and the second man in Al-Qaida Ayman al-Zawahiri (El-Nawawy & Iskander 2002).

On October 9, 2001, Al-Jazeera broadcast a taped statement by Al-Qaida's spokesman (ibid, 150). Al-Jazeera also aired on November 1, 2001 a faxed statement from ben Ladin and on November 3 in the same year aired a videotape of ben Ladin (ibid, 153).

But one of the most important tapes aired by Al-Jazeera was on December 27, 2001, when the Americans priced ben Ladin's head at US \$25 million, and when there was no news about him and there were rumours of his death (Miles 2005).

Remarkably, between September 2001 and 2006, "ben Ladin has released at least eighteen statements on video or audio tape, which have reached audiences of tens of millions as those statements are relayed around the globe by the BBC, CNN, Al-Jazeera and other television networks" (Bergen, 2006, xxvi).

In providing the one of the reasons of Al-Jazeera's fame, Warren (2003) argues that, "As the only broadcaster permitted by the Taliban to operate in Kabul, Al-Jazeera has captured worldwide fame with exclusive pictures of bombing raids and air defences, as well as – more controversially– its transmission of taped messages from the leaders of Al-Qaida" (pp. 30-31).

In their war against Al-Qaida and Taliban movement in Afghanistan, the Americans bombed Al-Jazeera's bureau in Kabul on November 12, 2001 (Miles, 2005). The American officials in Pentagon justified the raid and accused Al-Jazeera of supporting Al-Qaida and contacting Taliban (Cole, 2006).

Notably, Al-Jazeera does not only transmit Al-Qaida messages. For example, on October 24, 2002 Al-Jazeera aired videotape made by Chechen rebels (Dolnik & Fitzgerald, 2008). However, Fotion et al. (2007) point out there is a relationship between many Chechen Rebels and Al-Qaida. Based on this information, it could be concluded from this relationship that Al-Qaida either helped Chechen Rebels to transmit their message through Al-Jazeera or it inspired Chechen Rebels to send their message to Al-Jazeera. In the trial of former Al-Jazeera reporter in Afghanistan, Tayseer Alluni, the Spanish authorities found in

2005 that the terrorist Abu Dahdah (who is considered one of Al-Qaida's members) was keeping Alluni informed "on issues such as 'the favourable situation for the mujahideen in Chechnya', or on 'the mujahideen in Bosnia' and provided Alluni with videotapes featuring foreign Jihadi fighters in Bosnia" (Lia, 2008, p. 194).

When it reports on the "war on terrorism", Al-Jazeera uses the phrase "so-called terrorism". Ahmad Sheikh, deputy editor for Al-Jazeera, discusses how the network uses the term of terrorism, "When it is an American official or someone is saying it, we keep it as terrorism right? But when we are quoting one of them, we say 'what he called terrorism'. We do not use the word ourselves, because (...) this controversial. Can we agree, first of all, on a definition of what a terrorist act is?" (Japerson & El-Kikhia, 2003, p. 125).

This issue of reporting terrorism, where there is no common definition of terrorism, had been discussed previously in the last section. As result, it is the responsibility of Al-Jazeera to define its understanding of terrorism instead of providing illogical excuse by blaming the others.

3.2 Al-Jazeera's Defense of Airing terrorists' Messages

Al Jazeera offers three main arguments to defend its policy of airing interviews and other material sourced from Al-Qaida. These arguments are: Freedom of Speech, Scoop and Contrast Coverage.

3.2.1 Freedom of Speech

Al-Jazeera is adopting the freedom of speech media policy. This policy has been enhanced since the September 2001 attacks, when the United States announced the 'war on terror.' Arabs were against the invasion of Afghanistan and the regimes of the Gulf States felt confident enough within their societies to permit their media a degree of freedom to do what they, as regimes, could not do, by criticizing US policies (Japerson & El-Kikhia, 2003).

Also, Al-Jazeera's motto is 'The Opinion and the other Opinion'. That's why the channel base its excuse in transmitting Al-Qaida messages. The Emir of Qatar, Sheikh Hamad ben Khalifa Al-Thani argues that, "Ben Ladin is a part of the conflict and his opinions must be heard" (Miles, 2005, p. 123). Also, Al-Jazeera news editor Ahmad Sheikh states the channel's media policy, "We believe in objectivity, integrity and presenting all points of view – including both ben Ladin and George W. Bush" (ibid, 124).

Wadah Khanfar, the network's managing editor, in October 2004, points out that Al-Jazeera's editorial policy aims to gain credibility through providing comprehensive and balanced news (Barkho, 2006).

In his providing the reason of why the channel airs ben Ladin videotapes, Al-Jazeera's editor-in-chief Ibrahim Helal argues, "...Even the politicians in the West need to know him [ben Ladin]; they need to know what Al-Qaida thinks. We are going to know the other side of the story" (El-Nawawy & Iskander, 2002, p. 148).

However, the main point is not related to Al-Jazeera's argument to deliver both sides of the story. It hinges on the fact that how Al-Jazeera should cover the terrorist reports without contributing to their acts directly or indirectly. Al-Jazeera is not free if it reports terrorist activities and messages irresponsibly. The channel claims balance and equity in its motto. Based on this policy, the balance means equity between terrorists and victims, invaders and defenders. Such media policy adopted by Al-Jazeera may serve entirely the terrorists' agenda.

3.2.2 Scoop and Contrast Coverage

In screening the terrorist messages, especially ben Ladin's tapes, Al-Jazeera seeks to make what can be called in journalism a 'scoop.' Sheikh Hamad ben Thamer Al-thani, chairman of Al-Jazeera's board, emphasizes this journalistic concept, "Any [media] organization that was able to obtain such a scoop would not hesitate to accept; broadcasting videos of ben Ladin is no different from CNN's broadcasting speeches of Saddam Hussein during the

1991 Gulf War” (El-Nawawy & Iskander 2002, 148).

In the political sphere, locally and globally, Al-Jazeera is biased culturally to Qatari point of view and consequently the Arab point of view (Aday, Livingston, & Hebert, 2005). In this context, Seib (2005) argues that the reason for such bias is the emphasis of Al-Jazeera on the mood on “the Arab street” (p. 602). However, the ‘Arab street’ signifies the point of view adopted by the majority of Arabs, not the majority of the Arab governments.

Seib (2008) observes that Al-Jazeera has built a cohesive virtual community of viewers. Thus, this virtual community requires a steady flow of messages and among them terrorists’ messages. However, Al-Jazeera considers the concerns of the audience in its messages (El-Nawawy & Powers, 2008). This strategy serves in creating the audience solidarity with the media outlet (Weimann & Winn, 1994).

The ‘scoop’ and meeting the needs of ‘the Arab street’ do not mean that Al-Jazeera can screen terrorism freely. ‘Scoop’ gives Al-Jazeera the stipulated fame, but the fame would be bloody when it reports terrorism in an irresponsible way. Also, many channels attempt to meet the audience’s interests, however, Al-Jazeera creates its own audience who will accept whatever the channel screens and this is one of the dangerous issues when the Qatari based satellite reports terrorists’ messages.

Following the first aired message after the start of the American war on Afghanistan in 2001, Al-Jazeera was criticized because it gave ben Ladin the opportunity to state that the war is “religious” (Zayani, 2005).

In the line of contrast coverage, Al-Jazeera attempts to change the angle of coverage during the war on terrorism. In its coverage of the war on Afghanistan, Al-Jazeera has sympathized with civilians. Japerson and El-Kikhia (2003) point out that the “primary contrast in news coverage and framing is that Al-Jazeera did not gloss over a humanistic portrayal of the consequences of war... It has succeeded in making US and European media services take notice [in order to develop] a more balanced reporting of events” (p. 129).

Remarkably, Al-Jazeera in Afghanistan succeeded in presenting a new angle of coverage of the war. It may be crucial for any media outlet to sympathize with the civilians and victims, because they suffer during the conflict. In fact, the channel is confronting the Western monopoly in its coverage of the war in the Middle East. However, Al-Jazeera's exclusive access to Al-Qaida messages leads to accusations against it from some scholars who praised this sympathetic policy with the civilians and victims.

3.3 Al-Jazeera and Al-Qaida

One of the basic issues, which were discussed early in this research, is the media responsibility in reporting terrorism. In Al-Jazeera's case, there are two major elements observed by academics and researchers. These elements are Al-Jazeera's sympathy with terrorists and Al-Jazeera's exploitation by Al-Qaida. However, it is crucial to shed light on Al-Qaida's media strategy before discussing the accusations against Al-Jazeera of sympathizing and supporting terrorism.

3.3.1 Al-Qaida's Media Strategy

Al-Qaida's media strategy provides an example on how a terrorist organization exploits media outlets. Understanding Al-Qaida's media strategy is a key in showing whether Al-Jazeera TV channel is supporting terrorism or not. Academics, researchers and journalists have written about Al-Qaida's media strategy and Al-Qaida's leader, Osama ben Ladin, particularly after the September attacks.

In 1996, Abdel Bari Atwan, editor-in-chief of Al-Quds Al-Arabi, which is a well-known Arabic newspaper based in London, was invited by Khalid Al-Fawaz to interview ben Ladin. Al-Fawaz was the director of ben Ladin's office in Oxford Street in London. This office was the United Kingdom's branch of Al-Qaida's Reform and Advice Committee. This office in London was opened in 1994 and closed in 1998. Atwan (2006) points out that ben Ladin seems to have developed a very good sense of how to use the media over

the years, and when he decided to declare war on the United States, he wanted to be known the world over.

In similar vein, Gunaratna (2002) observes that when ben Ladin was in Sudan in the 1990s his organization “began to spread its network worldwide, developing an unprecedented communication network linking its regional offices in London, New York, Turkey and other centres” (p. 35).

Nacos argues that, “Al-Qaida timed that attacks [on September 11, 2001] in order to achieve maximum television coverage, most particularly through presentations on the evening news bulletins” (Lewis 2005, 25).

However, Al-Qaida does not rely only on sending messages to media outlets. It has its own media outlet, which is a website, called Al-Sahab, to transmit messages. In this regard, Riedel (2008) points out that “Al-Qaida propaganda machine, al-Sahab (the clouds), has only grown more influential and robust ... and its technical expertise has increased at an impressive rate. Even its logo now appears on coffee mugs, just as at CNN or Fox. A new message comes out every seventy two hours” (p. 123).

Notably, Al-Qaida has invented a new style of media propaganda following the start of the world war on terrorism in 2001 (Kepel and Millelli, 2008). Thus, Al-Qaida’s speech is concentrated on the idea that, “The United States wants to kill Muslims and control their world to exploit their resources” (Riedel, 2008, p. 135). This propaganda was one of the basic codes in ben Ladin’s videotapes, because he presented himself as a charismatic Muslim leader (Suter, 2008).

The American officials after September attacks warned from Al-Qaida propaganda (Dadge, 2006). The then White House Secretary, in 2001, Ari Fleisher, said, “At best, Osama ben Ladin’s message is propaganda, calling on people to kill Americans. At worst, he could be issuing orders” (El-Nawawy & Iskander 2002, p. 179).

This fear would seem real according to Qureshi (2009) who provides a remarkable

evidence about the importance of media in Al-Qaida's actions. He (ibid) argues that,

“The critical role of the media is well understood by the Salafi groups that wage an international Jihad against their perceived enemies throughout the world. The certainty of this axiom in Al-Qaida’s philosophy is evident in the fact that, even before the spectacular 9/11 attacks, one of four committees that formed its organizational structure was tasked with media and publicity. The importance behind that action was stressed in a letter sent by Ayman al-Zawahiri to Abu Musab al-Zarqawi where Zawahiri said that the media represent two thirds of the battle, as well as in a speech made by Osama ben Ladin in 2002 where he argued that, the time has come to have the media take its rightful place, to carry out its required role in confronting this aggressive campaign and the open declared Crusader war by all means that can be seen, heard, and read” (p. 238).

Al-Zawahiri, who is the second-in-command in Al-Qaida, provides clear evidence in his message about the importance of media for his organization to win the war. This means that media is one of the main elements in Al-Qaida's activities. It seems that Al-Qaida is looking to win the media battle to gain the upper hand in its global war.

3.3.2 Al-Jazeera and Sympathy with Al-Qaida

As some academics and researchers argue previously that Al-Jazeera is sympathizing with civilians in Afghanistan, there are others who argue that Al-Jazeera and its staff are sympathizing with terrorists (Paletz and Rickershauser, 2003). In his interview with the then UK Prime Minister Tony Blair, Sami Haddad, the presenter of 'More than one Opinion' on Al-Jazeera, has compared in his questions some terrorist organizations in the Middle East to the French fighters, who fought the Nazis in 1940s (Miles, 2005).

In a similar vein, the sympathy can be sketched in the relationship between journalists and terrorists. Tatham (2006) comments on the attendance of Al-Jazeera journalist, Ahmad Zeidan - who produced the documentary 'Ben Ladin Unmasked' - the wedding feast of ben Ladin's son, "While the channel would no doubt argue that this was merely the action of an enterprising journalist cultivating his contacts, there are others to whom this provide 'evidence' of a deeper sympathy within the channel and among its staff for ben Ladin and his ideals" (p. 127).

This accusation against Al-Jazeera's staff is not unique as shown previously regarding the case of Tayseer Alluni, the former head of Al-Jazeera's bureau in Afghanistan, was arrested by Spanish authorities in September 2004 and accused with cooperation with terrorists (Lia, 2008).

On contrary to the argument that Al-Jazeera sympathizes with terrorists, Miles (2005) argues that the Qatari government uses Al-Jazeera channel as a political tool to anger some regional countries, especially Saudi Arabia and Kuwait, by airing ben Ladin's terrorist messages, "For these two countries, televising ben Ladin is an unforgivable offence" (p. 52). Thus, the then Saudi Interior Minister in the late of 1990s, Prince Nayef, said, "That channel is distinguished high-quality product, but it serves up poison on a silver platter" (ibid, 53).

The major outcome of this debate hinges on the fact that Al-Jazeera has offered Al-Qaida a secure access to transmit its messages to the globe. As result, it is difficult to argue that Al-Jazeera sympathizes with terrorists although some of its journalists have been accused of supporting terrorism.

3.3.3 Al-Jazeera Exploited by Al-Qaida

Some academics argue that Al-Qaida is exploiting Al-Jazeera. Lawrence (2005) points out that, "Ben Ladin and his associates have crafted a series of carefully staged statements designed for the new media, especially video recordings distributed via Al-Jazeera" (p. xi).

In this vein, Timmerman (2003) finds out that Al-Qaida is exploiting Al-Jazeera by sending the channel reports for airing, “On state-sponsored Al-Jazeera television portrayed complacently as the ‘CNN of the Arab world’ by mainstream media organizations in the United States and Europe, Ben Ladin and Muslim preachers who openly sympathize spread their message to the Arab masses and intellectual elites” (p. 3).

Sharp (2003) numerates many reasons why Al-Qaida chooses Al-Jazeera as a conduit for its messages,

“Many analysts believe that Al-Qaida was attracted to Al-Jazeera’s large Arabic-speaking audience. Observers also speculated that Al-Jazeera, eager to make headlines and without rigorous governmental scrutiny, was in a position to broadcast the Ben Ladin tapes, as opposed to the more cautious Arab state media. Some analysts considered that Al-Qaida would have found Al-Jazeera to be sympathetic to its cause based on the network’s past coverage of Iraq in 1998. One theory explaining the Al-Jazeera - Ben Ladin connection comes from Al-Jazeera’s London Bureau Chief, Yosri Fouda, who interviewed two of Al-Qaida’s top leaders, Khalid Sheikh Mohammed and Ramzi bin Al-Sheeba (both are now in U.S. custody). Fouda had been chosen by Al Qaida’s leaders to tell their story” (p. 9).

However, Al-Jazeera’s staff denies any sort of exploitation by Al-Qaida. Al-Jazeera’s editor-in-chief Ibrahim Helal comments on why the channel transmits Al-Qaida messages, “The supporter of ben Ladin tried to deliver his messages in any possible way to the world. They have contacted some other Arab networks before seeking Al-Jazeera, but those networks refuse to communicate with them because ‘they are terrorists’. For us they are terrorists and we are journalists looking for news” (El-Nawawy & Iskander 2002, p. 155).

In Helal’s comment, Al-Jazeera admits that it is screening terrorists’ messages. This means

that the channel knows what it is doing in reporting terrorism. But Helal does not provide evidence that Al-Qaida is not exploiting Al-Jazeera.

Likewise Helal, the senior program producer at Al-Jazeera Ibrahim Hassan denies the allegations that Al-Qaida is exploiting Al-Jazeera, “I do not think that Ben Ladin and the Taliban have used us to transmit their propaganda. In fact we have used them to gain our international reputation” (Bessaïso, 2005, p. 163). Hassan provides an argument that Al-Jazeera grasps fame from airing Al-Qaida messages.

In a nutshell, Al-Qaida seeks to air its messages to the globe through Al-Jazeera as well as the channel airs the terrorists’ message to gain a global fame.

3.3.4 Al-Jazeera’s Mechanism in Airing ben Ladin’s Tapes

As was shown previously, Al-Jazeera is always trying to make a ‘scoop’ and gaining fame by airing ben Ladin videotapes. But the important question is: how does the channel receive ben Ladin’s videotapes?

Burleigh (2008) explains how Al-Jazeera receives these tapes, “Trusted Arab or Afghan cameramen are also brought in to record major statements by Ayman al-Zawahiri or the latest front man... The films are copied to CDs and then passed on through several hands to the television station Al-Jazeera” (pp. 470-471).

Remarkably, Al-Jazeera refuses to declare how it receives the tapes. Generally, it refers in its news bulletins that the channel received the tapes from an ‘unknown source.’ However, the question is: What are the media standards which lie behind airing the tapes?

Al-Jazeera’s editor-in-chief Ibrahim Helal explains the mechanism of airing Ben Ladin videotapes, “We don’t just take any tape that comes to our offices or to the network and put it on air. Before that, we have a meeting to discuss how we should treat the news, and not be subject to the propaganda... We try to find the right people to talk to us on air... To air statements without any comments, without any opposing statements or view points or analysis, that’s when it’s propaganda” (El-Nawawy & Iskander, 2002, p. 154).

It seems from Helal's explanation that Al-Jazeera is airing the tapes in a professional way to avoid any accusation against the channel of supporting terrorism. But there is one confusing issue, when Helal denies rumours that Al-Jazeera received the ben Ladin tape before the September 2001 attacks which contains threats to the United States (El-Nawawy & Iskander, 2002).

While there is no tangible evidence that Al-Jazeera received any videotape from ben Ladin before the September attacks, there is a precedent that Al-Jazeera interviewed ben Ladin in 1998 and aired it in June 1999 (ibid). In another occasion, Al-Jazeera waited several days, before it aired ben Ladin videotape, which received on November 3, 2001 (ibid).

Furthermore, Al-Jazeera never aired Tayseer Alluni's interview with ben Ladin on October 20, 2001. Al-Jazeera did not inform CNN about the interview, where the two channels have had an agreement, and refused to air the interview due to "editorial standards" (Miles, 2005). However, CNN obtained the videotaped interview from what so called an independent source and aired excerpts on January 31 and February 1, 2002 (El-Nawawy & Iskander, 2002).

Notably, Helal contradicts himself when he says that he had several videotapes of ben Ladin and Al-Jazeera did not broadcast them, because they were deemed not news worthy or of poor technical quality (ibid, 153).

There are some questions about the above debate: What are the 'editorial standards' that prevent Al-Jazeera from airing the interview and not telling CNN about it, while the latter received it from an unknown source? Does CNN know the value and the importance of this exclusive interview with ben Ladin more than Al-Jazeera? What are other parts of the interview which CNN did not air? By comparing CNN and Al-Jazeera, it could be argued that Al-Jazeera lost its credibility when it hid the interview from CNN, while the latter dealt with the interview in a professional and responsible way, filtering what it wants to screen.

But there is still an important question: If the rumours prove to be facts and Al-Jazeera had obtained ben Ladin videotape, which contains threats to the United States, before September 11, 2001, what is the judgment in this case?

It would be argued that there are two points of view. Firstly, Al-Jazeera was not professional enough and did not know how worthy that tape was. Secondly, the channel was collaborating with Al-Qaida to air the videotape after the attacks. In this case, the second point would be the probable one, because both Al-Jazeera and Al-Qaida are seeking to maximize their publicity, and this was shown clearly in the previous discussions about Al-Qaida's media strategy, Al-Jazeera's fame and Al-Jazeera's reasons to transmit terrorists' messages. In addition, the case of Alluni's interview with ben Ladin supports the possibility that Al-Jazeera may have received ben Ladin's tape before the September attacks.

3.3.5 Is Al-Jazeera Supporting Terrorism?

It could be observed clearly that Al-Jazeera is not a terrorist media outlet. Terrorist outlets are formed by terrorists themselves or support a terrorist agenda. Remarkably, Al-Jazeera's transmitting of terrorists' messages has launched an academic debate whether this media outlet is supporting terrorism or not. Even from the military perspective, Kumashiro (2005) argues that Al-Jazeera is inhibiting the American strategy in its 'War on Terrorism.'

Al-Jazeera is called ben Ladin's 'mouthpiece' in the West (Miles, 2005). Furthermore, Al-Jazeera was condemned in the Western talk shows as a mouthpiece of terror and some wondered if ben Ladin might be behind this channel (ibid).

Notably, the existence of Al-Jazeera creates ben Ladin's image in the minds of people around the globe. In this vein, Seib (2008) argues that ben Ladin, without Al-Jazeera, will be a "cranky guy in a cave" (p. 188).

The fame of Al-Jazeera and the size of its audience are tempting to any message's sender, including ben Ladin (Ajami, 2001). Rushing (2007) aligns with this argument pointing out

that, “The myth that Al-Jazeera is a tool for the terrorists thrives to this day, probably because the network remains the best method for reaching a widespread Arab audience” (p. 154).

As shown previously, there are accusations against Al-Jazeera, because it provides ben Ladin an access to say that the war on Afghanistan is ‘religious’ (Bessaiso, 2005). Other scholars, such as Ajami (2006) and Phares (2008) conclude that Al-Jazeera is inciting terrorism and jihadism respectively.

Reporting terrorists’ messages, especially ben Ladin’s ones, will still generate accusations against Al-Jazeera, because it is the only channel that receives ben Ladin’s videotapes (Carney, 2006.)

However, Miles (2006) argues that Al-Jazeera is not supporting terrorism,

“When Al-Jazeera offers its estimated 50 million viewers exclusive interviews of Osama ben Ladin, it’s easy to confuse access with endorsement. And when a journalist who conducts those interviews is jailed for collaboration with al Qaida, as Tayseer Alluni..., the line between impartial observer and impassioned supporter is certainly blurred... The network has never supported violence against the United States. Not once have its correspondents praised attacks on coalition forces in Iraq. The network has never captured an attack on the coalition ‘live,’ and there’s no evidence Al-Jazeera has known about any attack beforehand. Despite claims to the contrary, the network has never aired footage of a beheading... Allegations of supporting terrorism remain just that—allegations” (p. 20).

Miles’s argument that Al-Jazeera does not praise terrorists’ attacks seems as a paralogism. Al-Jazeera by opening its air to terrorists, and their supporters, provides indirect praise to terrorism. Such indirect praise may have a bad influence on the audience.

Meanwhile, Zayani (2006) does not blame Al-Jazeera for its airing terrorists' messages, but he blames the Arabic regimes,

“If Al-Jazeera gives the impression sometimes that it is ‘the ben Ladin channel’ it is not because it broadcasts Al-Qaida tapes or toes an anti-Western line, but primarily because the political institutions in the Arab World are largely deficient and do not allow for real participation or promote a governing system based on checks and balances. Not surprisingly then, media democracy in the Arab autocracies often results in a media mobocracy. To ignore this point is to risk treating the problem as the symptom of the problem as the problem itself and, in the process, reduce a complex institutional political problem to a purely ‘media effects issue’” (p. 187).

It could be observed that Zayani does not deny that Al-Jazeera is supporting terrorism. However, by comparing Miles and Zayani's arguments it can be argued that Al-Jazeera gains viewers and doing “scoop” through airing Al-Qaida's tapes and messages. The intersection of interests provides Al-Qaida a unique access to the world and Al-Jazeera a controversial global fame. Al-Jazeera is likely supporting terrorism, because it transmits Al-Qaida's messages freely, refusing to call it a terrorist organization.

4. Conclusion

This short research discussed one of the contemporary cases about the relationship between a media outlet and terrorism. The case was about Al-Jazeera satellite, which grasped fame after its exclusive reporting of terrorists' messages, particularly Al-Qaida's videotapes in the world of the 'war on terror' following the September attacks.

To answer the research question and achieve its aims, this research presented discussions from researchers, academics, politicians and journalists about media responsibility when reporting terrorism. It traced the academic discussions historically regarding the relationship between media and terrorism since the 1960s, shedding light on some cases to contextualize the research.

Al-Jazeera and terrorists, the reasons why Al-Jazeera carries reports of terrorists, Al-Qaida's media strategy, and Al-Jazeera's media policy in transmitting ben Ladin videotapes were discussed in this study.

This research concluded that Al-Jazeera benefitted from airing Al-Qaida's messages, particularly ben Ladin videotapes to grasp global fame. As result, Al-Jazeera unwittingly has supported Al-Qaida which knows the importance of media to achieve its goals.

Based on the discussions of the presented arguments, this research argued that Al-Jazeera is likely supporting terrorists, because it transmits their messages freely, providing an excuse that there is no global consensus on a definition of terrorism.

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